

cel 3/4

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1C Arrows point to lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 2: I-ASD-3 C1, NI1, Lane 3: Sib-3 C1 NI2,

Lane 4: Sib-3 C2 NI1 , Lane 5: Sib-3C2, NI2

Lane 6: I-ASD-3 C1, NI2, Lane 7: I-ASD-3 C2, NI1, Lane 8: I-ASD-3 C2 NI2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Amn
b-actin

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1C -GAPDH for P-AKT Film

phospho blot

T

REC1

3

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1C Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 2: I-ASD-3 C1, NI1, Lane 3: Sib-3 C1 NI2,

Lane 4: Sib: Sib-3 C2 NI1 , Lane 5: Sib-3C2, NI2

Lane 6: I-ASD-3 C1, NI2, Lane 7: I-ASD-3 C2, NI1, Lane 8: I-ASD-3 C2 NI2

Bolded text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

T

T

Gel 3/4

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1C -Total AKT Film

1500

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1C Arrows point to lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 2: I-ASD-3 C1, NI1, Lane 3: Sib-3 C1 NI2,
Lane 4: Sib-3 C2 NI1 , Lane 5: Sib-3C2, NI2
 Lane 6: **I-ASD-3 C1, NI2**, Lane 7: I-ASD-3 C2, NI1, Lane 8: I-ASD-3 C2 NI2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

3/20'

AKT

Fam 1012 Blot
total blot
Setz

Setz Akt + 56 blot ERK blot
5 ser total blot gel 44

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1C-GAPDH for Total AKT Film

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1C Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 2: I-ASD-3 C1, NI1, Lane 3: Sib-3 C1 NI2,
Lane 4: Sib-3 C2 NI1, Lane 5: Sib-3C2, NI2
Lane 6: I-ASD-3 C1, NI2, Lane 7: I-ASD-3 C2, NI1, Lane 8: I-ASD-3 C2 NI2

Bolded text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

35cc

2 Sec